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Adoption of Digital Wallet Systems and Gross Domestic Product Increase in Nigeria: An Exploratory Survey

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Abstract

This research evaluated empirically the adoption of Digital Wallet systems and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Increase in Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted and data were sourced through questionnaire administration and analysis was by a veritable statistical instrument referred to as Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC), denoted with 'r' letter. The findings exhibited a robust structure showing that an overall 55.31% of total respondents affirmed that the use of Digital Wallets in operations facilitated GDP Increase. The empirically estimated model showed a PPMCC or 'r' coefficient of 0.7574 attesting to a strong and healthy linear relationship. Additionally, the Coefficient of Determination (r^2) standing at 0.5737 or 57.37% implied that the variable Digital Wallet systems explained 57.37% variation in GDP Increase. In other words, the independent variable, Digital Wallet systems predicted 57.37% of the dependent variable, GDP Increase. From these reports, we rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that Digital Wallets adoption made relevant and great contributions to boosting GDP Increase in Nigeria. We therefore recommend that an effective enlightenment and education be carried out to stimulate rapid adoption of Digital Wallet systems with a view to facilitating economic activities and thus GDP Increase in the Nigerian economy

Keywords: Digital Wallet Systems, Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) codes, Apple Pay, PayPal, Google Pay, GDP Increase, Nigeria

American Economic Association JEL Classification: G1, G2, G

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital Wallet systems utilizing software programs to aid commercial transactions are becoming very popular in global financial markets. Obviously, they are now very importance in fastening economic activities. There is increased interest in their usage and the focus of current researches on them is evolving with the hope of meeting the needs of business units and boosting output of nations. It is pursuant to this that this research sought to explore Digital Wallet systems in commercial operations and Gross Domestic Product Increase with a view to enhancing and repositioning the Nigerian economy. The study aligns with United Nations General Assembly (UN-GA) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) being advocated to assist nations achieve sustainable economic development. Global Rewilding Initiative (2024) posits that in 2015, UN-GA resolved and endorsed seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to enable nations of the world enhance their economies. For emerging and developing economies like Nigeria, the most crucial goals that has serious bearing on the Nigerian economy were GOAL 1: No Poverty; a goal that seeks to eradicate extreme poverty; GOAL 2: Zero

Hunger; targeted at ending hunger and GOAL 8: Decent Work and Economic growth; aimed to promote and sustain inclusive economic growth.

Digital Wallet systems also referred simply to as Mobile Payment systems exist as financial applications (finapps), that is, software programs used to expedite and simplify financial transactions, administer financial services and manage financial data. The phrases, Digital Wallet systems and Mobile Payment systems are used mutually or interchangeably in the study to mean the same concept. These electronic applications allow users to make monetary transactions cum operations utilizing their mobile gadgets, instruments and devices, help households or organizations to manage and analyze financial data, make informed investments decisions and optimize financial performance. Digital Wallet offers a range of benefits which include: security, convenience as a result of automation, cost savings, accessibility, increased efficiency, improved financial management, et cetera. Kagan (2024) opined that Digital Wallets serve as financial applications that allow economic units to store financial information in a digital wallet, accomplish transactions, and trail payment past records on instrument like phones and tablets. As a financial application, a Digital Wallet functions are diverse and may also be used to accomplish such tasks as investment research analysis, budgeting and expense tracking. Dipo, (2013), averred that Digital Wallets systems utilize differing technologies which includes:

- **Near Field Communication (NFC):** The technology that allows contactless payments, that is, payments conducted without human to human contact or that do not require contact to be operated and accomplished.
- **Quick Response Codes (QR codes):** This scans codes that can be read by mobile phones to initiate transactions. QR codes usually consist of payment details and information as in Credit cards details or payment links.
- **Mobile apps:** These are dedicated apps for transactions such as Paypal, Google pay, apple Pay, et cetera.
- **Short Message Service (SMS)/Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD):** Theses technologies use text messages or USSD codes for transactions.
- **Tokenization:** The technology that replaces sensitive data such as Credit card numbers or Personal identifiable number (PIN) information with unique tokens. These token have no intrinsic value or meaning which makes them useless to unauthorized persons

So, Digital Wallets, otherwise, Mobile payment systems operations constitute a kind of banking service delivery that permits individuals and business units to gain access to their bank accounts and carry out financial operations and transactions using their mobile tools and phones. Ritzén, & Hussein, (2021) affirmed that Digital Wallet can be possible through a variety of Mobile payment methods or systems which includes: Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) codes and Short Message Service (SMS) texting, Apple Pay, PayPal, WeChat Pay, Google Pay, etcetera as earlier asserted. These mobile payment systems have been widely known and used globally because of their flexibility, speed, convenience and accessibility. The systems also provide users with benefit such as easy transfer of funds, online purchase, speed transaction with less cost and it is time and resource saving. As a result of increased completion in the banking industry, it became necessary to adopt Digital Wallets in operations in Nigeria. Digital wallets as powerful operational tools help to push development and support growth in an economy by the nature of products and services they deliver and the way they are packaged and consumed. This informed Banks and other businesses to rapidly adopt e-Commerce and introduce Digital Wallet systems to enhance efficiency of their day to day activities. Figure 1.1 defines and illustrates a Digital Wallet.

Figure 1.1 Digital Wallet defined and illustrated

Source: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/d/digital-wallet.asp>, (2024)

To commence Digital Wallet services or operations in the Nigerian economy, individual must first register with their banking institution. Once they have been registered, they gain access to their operating accounts that allows them perform financial transactions either with their mobile tools or phones, tablets or mini-computers. Kagan (2024) argued that Digital wallet or apps can be used to make inquiry on account balances, effect transfer of funds between banking institutions accounts, pay utility bills, and make settlements and purchases. The wallet is a convenient and widely available option for individuals who want to access their bank account and perform financial transactions on the go. It is often more secured than traditional methods such as using cash or cheques. It has enhanced security features like tokenization and biometric authentication. It offers additional features and benefits because it offers individuals the ability to track spending, set alerts and access account information. Appah, Tebepah, & Newstyle. (2023) affirmed that Digital wallet or Mobile payment benefits are much more and also include creating convenience – that is easy transactions that do not need physical cash or cards. It involves and allows fast transaction processing and so it is widely accepted in carrying out transactions of any type. The system is applicable in store purchases, person-to-person payments, online payments and transactions, bill payments and even public transportation. As the systems are evolving, we expect more innovative and creative features and increased adoption globally.

In this study Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Increase represents the explained variable. GDP Increase also known as economic growth indicates growth in the total value or amount of services and goods produced and manufactured within a country's borders over a specific time period, usually a year. GDP Increase can be determined by various factors which may include: increase in investments, increase consumer spending, growth in government spending, improved productivity, good implementation of monetary and fiscal policies, technological advancement, boost in net exports, favourable business environments, et cetera. Blanchard (2011), affirmed that when the economy experience GDP growth, it helps to improve higher standard of living, rise in income, increased employment opportunities, economic stability is enhanced, infrastructural development is improved and government revenues are as well improved. It is therefore good that a country should strive to achieve sustainable GDP growth by formulating balanced economic policies, promoting innovation and technology, investing in human capital, fostering global trade and cooperation and encouraging sustainable practices. The proper implementation of most of the aforementioned activities appear lacking in Nigeria. That coupled with the poor management of the demanding sectors of the economy as with the banking industry and the indigent monetary policies implementation by successive governments have contributed

immensely to economic retardation that is kind of laying foundation for economic recession. Conformance to the foregoing facts further buttressed reasons why this study seeks to assess Digital wallet or Mobile Payment Systems and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Increase in Nigeria. The objective of the study is therefore derived from the topic and it is to determine the effect of the use of Digital wallets, otherwise Mobile payment systems on GDP Increase in Nigeria.

1.1 Hypothesis Formulation

Based on the foregoing discussions, we formulated a null hypothesis to be tested to enable us elicit inferences and draw logical and reasonable conclusions. The null hypothesis thus states as follows:

H0: No significant relationship exists between Digital wallet system operations and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Increase in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURES REVIEW

It is obvious that the adoption of Digital Wallet systems can play great roles in an economy by enhancing, speeding and facilitating successful financial transactions and business operations. According to Gomber, Koch, & Siering, (2017), Digital Wallet operates as digital finance and it encompasses a multitude of new financial businesses and products, finance-based software and new kinds of customer interactive communication systems delivered by Financial Technology (Fin-Tech) companies and innovative financial service providers. While there appear to be no standardized definition of Digital Wallet, there is some consensus amongst finance scholars that it encompasses all services, products, infrastructures, and technologies that allow business units, companies and individuals to have access to payment, saving and credit facilities by means of the internet (online) without visiting a bank branch or without dealing directly with the financial service providers. The adoption of Digital Wallet system has in several ways made relevant and important impact on commercial dealings, interactions and transactions and can be seen to have contributed much to GDP increase or growth. Zwingina, Onoh, & Ezechi (2015), highlighted some ways in which Digital wallets can immensely facilitate the growth of GDP and these include the following:

Increase financial inclusion: By expanding access to financial services especially for rural and underserved populations and this leads to increased economic activities.

Improved transaction efficiency: By facilitating faster and cheaper transactions thereby reducing friction and increasing the velocity of money.

Increased access to credit: By providing access to credit and loans thus supporting entrepreneurship and consumption.

Job creation: By creating new job opportunities in fin-tech, e-commerce and related industries in the economy. It supports e-commerce growth by expanding market access and opportunities for businesses

Financial deepening: By promoting financial deepening by way of increasing financial services thus leading to broader economic growth.

Innovation and entrepreneurship: By fostering innovation and entrepreneurship, thereby driving economic growth and development.

Digital Wallets has the potential of making positive and significant impact on GDP growth and contribute to a more vibrant and inclusive economy by increasing the efficiency of operation, creating access to credit and especially by improving financial inclusion. Barbesino, Cameran, and Gaudino, (2005), argued that services through the internet has become a very recognized channel of distribution for banking industry products in Europe and all traditional banking firms and new players are discovering its effectiveness compared with other channels. According to Saul, Susanna and Adeline (2017), Digital Wallets foster financial inclusion in developed and some developing economies by supplying cheap and secured methods of fund transfers and storing of monetary values. This is crucial in economies with large unbanked population and environments where demand for secured and cheap money transfer is high.

Individuals and even businesses often rely on mobile payment system transactions and this brings to fore financial inclusion benefits, advantages or gains because it enables households to purchase daily needs and necessary products, invest in assets, and raise their overall living standard. Therefore mobile payments via Digital Wallet channels can result in increased economic activities and enhance a country's economic growth. Accordingly, Dipo (2013), asserts that Digital Wallet operations are payment services operated under financial regulation and performed via mobile devices to speed up commercial transactions and in particular to fasten payments for transactions. Mobile phones play key roles in the initiation, authorization and consummation of the transactions. Mobile Payments or Digital Wallets are therefore substitutes or replacements for cash payments, cheques or credit cards. Consumers use their mobile devices to make payments in the stead of cash for a wide range of products and services and also to receive payments. This way, the adoption of Digital Wallet systems has also facilitated the concept of financial deepening, the process of increasing the size and complexity of a country's financial system. Demetriades & Hussein (1996) showed a bidirectional result between financial deepening and economic growth. Financial deepening in this context can be explained as an enlarged proportion or range of the financial sector activities in the economy such as bank deposit and bank credits and increased use of Digital Wallet instruments. A deepening financial market can facilitate and enhance economic growth by lowering the requirements and offering through Digital Wallets instruments economic services to a broader group of households and business firms that were previously unbanked although Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) are rare in such rural areas.

Most times Micro Finance firms promote financial offerings and services to rural dwellers and serve the population where banks are uncommon. One of the major and dominant ways that Digital Wallet transactions drive GDP Increase in these areas is through its power to affect economic productivity. Digital technologies have been known to facilitate and improve productivity by allowing businesses to integrate processes, have entry to new markets and enhance customer service. It is a candid fact that since the introduction of digital apps in Nigeria, it has aided quick business dealings and payments and settlements in the economy. The rapid change in technology has helped the people to a better communication cost saving and efficient business settlements. Mobile phones has also helped to empower women by participating in the labour market as e-commerce and online, entrepreneurs. Pursuant to World Development Report, (2016), Digital technologies have diffused very quickly into most regions of the world and have become so proliferated. The somewhat proliferation of digital technologies has closed the digital divide amongst firms and thus benefited everyone especially access to the internet. To get the best out of the digital revolution, companies may be required to work on strengthening regulations, ensure competition by developing workers' skills and be accountable. Mobile apps can help economic development by improving a firm's communication outlets with both customers and suppliers. The mobile apps create jobs and new businesses can be established because farmers, for instance can call or text to receive information on the cost of fruits and vegetables from the markets in the city instead of making time to travel back and forth. So, Digital Wallets operations can be said to have yielded so much dividends in aiding local, country and international financial transactions.

Figure 2.1 Sample of Digital Wallet Instruments exhibited

Source: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/wdr> (2024)

Dipo (2013) confirmed that access to Digital technology (Digi-Tech) and telecom infrastructure has strong impact on economic growth. He asserts that Digi-tech can significantly contribute to GDP growth by:

- Boosting productivity as automation and data analytics enhance efficiency and output.
- Driving innovation because digital technology allows new business models, products and services.
- Fostering entrepreneurship because digital platforms and tools facilitate startup growth and scalability.
- Enhancing trade as e-commerce and digital market places expand global trade opportunities.
- Creating new industries and jobs because Digi-Tech give rise to new sectors and employment opportunities.
- Improving data-driven decision making by enabling informed policies and business decisions.

According to Dipo (2013) Agent Banking (or branchless banking) uses Digital technology (Digi-Tech) to provide financial banking services by an authorized third agent to customers through a single business unit or distributed networks of retail or postal outlets.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

Research Methods presents the mechanisms and techniques utilized to carry out the study. The discussions here will be done in sub-sections for clarity of purpose.

3.1 Research Design, Population and Sample size

This study followed the 'Survey Research Design' considered extensively broad to provide intellectual and perfect understanding about the study population and methods of sourcing data. The study Population is a body, set or cluster of persons or a group of same species of organism or an aggregation of same types of items found in same location. In a more precise form, Creswell (2005), described Population as the broadest level in which an aggregation of individuals or things under study possess one trait and typical feature that separates them from other group. Since Digital Wallet transactions or mobile payments can allow banking transactions to be made by authorized third agents in single business units or networks of retail outlets such as Stores, Offices, Super markets, Kiosks, etc, the Population of the study consists of all Medium, Small and Micro (MSM) business units in Nigeria. The Sample population is drawn from the Population and it consists of all authorized

agents in MSM business units operating in commercial cities of Edo and Delta States of Nigeria. The spread of the Sample consists of six hundred (600) authorized agents operating in various MSM business units were adopted by rule of thumb in a simplified and experience-based approach that provides an acceptable benchmark or measure.

3.2 Sampling Techniques and Instruments

The Random sampling method and technique is most appropriate for a research study employing Survey design because the technique is considered free from partiality. So, it was adopted in this study for the collection of data from the Sample population. The sampling instrument is an analytical questionnaire designed into two separate segments - the demographic section and the questions with answer options section. The later section was designed in the pattern of ‘Item-Specific-Response-Options (ISRO) which pursuant to Wronski (2018) assertion interprets ‘Item specific’ to signify that response options are distinct to a particular sampling question. The ISRO tactics has a rating scale of five points categorized as: ‘Very Affirmative; Somewhat Affirmative; Neither Affirmative nor Negative; Somewhat Negative to Very Negative’. These rating points in the scale are weighted 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

3.3 Data analysis technique and model specification

The statistical tool of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) denominated with the letter ‘r’ was utilized for the empirical estimation of the research model. Boone and Boone (2012), affirmed that the PPMCC analysis technique is proper and suitable to evaluate a five point ISRO rating scale. Besides, Graeme, (2014) noted that among the most utilized indices for determining correlation coefficient is the PPMCC. When the product ‘r’ is squared’ it gives another measuring parameter known as the Coefficient of Determination (r²), also referred to as adjusted R-squared. These two parameters are employed in analyzing the relationship between the study variables.

With this background, the PPMCC model is specified and will be appraised to provide good information on how the variables correlate with particular reference to the direction and strength of relationship. Obadan, (2012), provided a mathematical model for computing the PPMCC or ‘r’ coefficient of the relationship between the variables as expressed in equation (1). This model employs data of variables expressed in absolute figures. Therefore the PPMCC or ‘r’ coefficient of correlation between variables Y and X can be computed using the following model:

$$\text{PPMCC or 'r'} = \frac{\sum (X - \bar{X})(Y - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum (X - \bar{X})^2 \sum (Y - \bar{Y})^2}} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation (1)}$$

Where: ‘r’ = Pearson’s Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient between X and Y variables

- X = Weighted Answer response options
- Y = Frequency of Answer response options
- ∑ = Summation sign
- \bar{X} = Mean of weighted Answer response options
- \bar{Y} = Mean of frequency of Answer response options

However, the mathematical model in equation (1) is somewhat complex and clumsy to compute and derive coefficients. In its stead, Obadan, (2012), provided an alternative diminished and easy to manipulate model in equation 2 that uses deviations from Means of variables being evaluated to compute PPMCC or ‘r’ coefficient. Equation 2 is given as follows:

$$\text{PPMCC or 'r'} = \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{\sum x^2 \sum y^2}} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation (2)}$$

Where x = X - \bar{X} (Deviation of Weighted Answer options from their mean)

$$y = Y - \bar{Y} \text{ (Deviation of Response Frequencies from their mean)}$$

3.4 Decision rule:

A decision rule applies to the computed value of ‘r’ Coefficient whose value falls within the range of -1 to +1. Pursuant to Obadan (2012), a decision is made following the specified rules as stated here under: When ‘r’ is:

- i. 0 (Zero), relationship does not exist between the variables.
- ii. +1, a perfect positive relationship exists.
- iii. -1, a perfect negative correlation exists.

As also reported by Obadan (2012), the effectiveness and potency of the derived coefficient is determined by the magnitude of the value of PPMCC or ‘r’. Therefore, based on the magnitude of the coefficient, the relationship between the variables under review may be determined as follows.

- $0.7 < 'r' < 1$: Strong correlation
- $0.5 < 'r' < 0.7$: Moderate correlation
- $0.3 < 'r' < 0.5$: Weak correlation
- $'r' < 0.3$: Very weak correlation

Note that the Coefficient of Determination (r^2), the second parameter to be derived from the model is arrived at when the ‘r’ coefficient is squared. These rules were adopted in discussing the research findings in subsequent section.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Presentation of data

As earlier stated, research data were assembled through questionnaire administration. Of the six hundred (600) questionnaires that were randomly administered to respondents in the Sample population, five hundred and seventy (575) were retrieved which accounted for 95.83% of all questionnaires distributed. By the rule of thumb, this percentage of retrieved questionnaires is large and suitable for analysis that could be of general application to the study population. The data obtained were first presented in a table with numeric numbers and their corresponding percentages as per total retrieved questionnaires. To distinguish the features of the answer options distinctively, the data expressed in percentages were again represented in a Column chart. The inquiry question in the questionnaire asked to capture the link between the use of Digital wallet systems in operation and GDP Increase in Nigeria states as follows:

‘How contented or unsatisfied would you assert that the use of Digital wallet Systems in transactions has facilitated Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Increase in Nigeria’.

Table 4.1 displays the response frequencies in numeric figures and in percentages to the answer options allocated to the question.

Table 4.1: Responses frequencies obtained.

	Response Frequencies	Response Frequencies in Percentages (%)
Very Contented	135	23.48%
Somewhat Contented	183	31.83%
Neither Contented nor Unsatisfied	101	17.56%
Somewhat Unsatisfied	99	17.22%
Very Unsatisfied	57	9.91%
Total	575	100.00 %

Source: Field Survey Report, 2024

Analyzing table 4.1 shows that 23.48% of total respondents are very contented and opined that Digital wallets adoption in operations has facilitated GDP Increase in the Nigerian economy. A larger group of respondents making up 31.48% believe to some extent that Digital wallet in commercial transactions has influenced economic growth. Collectively, the table revealed that 55.31% of total respondents are positive of the impact Digital wallets in operations have made to assist the progress of economic activities by facilitating general commercial transactions in the economy and to improve and promote economic growth. However, more about the characteristics of the response frequencies will be exhibited with the estimation of the empirical model when distinct coefficients are derived for PPMCC or (r) and the Coefficient of Determination (r²). We employed figure 4.1 to display distinctively the features of the response frequencies, the data expressed in percentages and represented in a column chart.

Figure 4.1 Responses frequencies represented in a column chart.

Source: Author’s computation, 2024

4.2 Model Estimation

The values of PPMCC or (‘r’) and the Coefficients of Determination (r²) used for results analyses were computed using the model specified in equation 2 in section three above. To enable us achieve this goal, table 4.2 is used to derive the sum totals (Σ) of the model components as therein computed.

Table 4.2: Derivation of sums (Σ) of model components

	X	Y	x = X - X̄	y = Y - Ȳ	xy	x ²	y ²
Very Satisfied	5	135	2	20	40	4	1600
Somewhat Satisfied	4	183	1	68	68	1	4624
Neither Satisfied nor Dissatisfied	3	101	00	-14	00	00	196
Somewhat Dissatisfied	2	99	-1	-16	16	1	256
Very Dissatisfied	1	57	-2	-58	116	4	3364
Total (Σ)	15	575	00	00	240	10	10040

Source: Authors’ computation, 2

024.

Mean of Weighted Answer Options;

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{n} = \frac{15}{5} = 3$$

$$\text{Mean of Frequency Response Options} \quad \bar{Y} = \frac{\sum Y}{n} = \frac{575}{5} = 115$$

$$\text{From equation 2, PPMCC or 'r'} = \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{\sum x^2 \sum y^2}} = \frac{240}{\sqrt{10 \times 10040}} = \frac{240}{316.86} = 0.7574$$

Therefore:

The Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC) or 'r' = 0.7574 and
The Coefficient of Determination (r^2) = $(0.7574)^2 = 0.5737$ or 57.37%.

5.0 DISCUSSIONS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Discussion of findings

We relied on the decision rule in section 3.4 to analyze results of this study particularly for the derived product of PPMCC or 'r'. To ease understanding, it might be good and necessary to explain what PPMCC) or 'r' measures. The value of 'r' coefficient shows the strength and tenacity of interrelationship and also the direction indicated by the linear relationship subsisting between two continuous variables being reviewed in the model. It gauges the extent to which the study variables progress and move together. On the other hand, the Coefficient of Determination (r^2) tells the proportion or degree of the divergence, variance or fluctuation in the dependent variable (Y) being explained and elucidated by the independent variable (X) in the model. The value of r^2 coefficient also determines the degree of the goodness of fit exhibited by the model which shows how robust the model truly is. Based on the decision rule and the forgoing, we attempt to present a logical discussion on the estimation results.

On estimation, the model produced a Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) or 'r' standing at 0.7574. The 'r' coefficient carries a positive sign, indicating the positive direction of the relationship. By interpretation, when the value is positive, it implies that an increase or rise in one variable induces an increases or rise in the other variable and a negative value means that the increase in one variable leads to a decrease in the other. Since the derived PPMCC or 'r' value in this study is positive, it implies therefore that the more the adoption and acquisition of Digital Wallet systems in operations and transactions in the economy, the more Gross Domestic Product will increase, in other words, the economy will grow. The positive coefficient indicates the degree at which the variables affect each other proportionately. Again, an 'r' coefficient with a magnitude of 0.7574 signifies a strong linear relationship. A high absolute value of 'r' close to 1 or -1 portent a strong relationship or correlation and a low absolute value close to 0 show a weak linear relationship or correlation. The high coefficient thus suggests that there is a strong linear relationship between Digital Wallet system operations and Economic growth. It means also that increase in the adoption of Digital Wallets could predict a corresponding increase in economic performance or GDP increase. The second measurement parameter is the Coefficient of Determination (r^2) standing at 0.5737 or 57.37%. Deductions from the decision rule indicate that an R-squared or r^2 of the magnitude of 0.5737 is a strong relationship. It implies that Digital Wallet system operations were able to explain 57.37% variation in GDP Increase in the economy of Nigeria. It shows again that the r^2 coefficient measured 57.37% of the goodness of fit of the model, meaning also that Digital wallet systems operation in Nigeria predicted and appropriated 57.37% of GDP Increase variable. A higher r^2 value would show a better fit and a value of 1.0 would means that the model fits perfectly.

The implications of these high coefficients and results mean that Digital wallet system, otherwise, Mobile payment system has played a significant role in driving economic growth in Nigeria. It has transformed and remodeled how financial services are evaluated particularly in an emerging economy like Nigeria where traditional banking infrastructure appears to still dominate in the operational system. In a broader perspective, the adoption of Digital wallet systems in commercial transactions even in municipal areas has facilitated and increased financial inclusion concept being initiated in the economy by reaching individual who previously had

limited access to banking and financial services. In general Digital Wallets has also increased banking efficiency, reduced transaction costs and eliminated long queues and the paper work of the banking systems. In summary, Digital wallet systems in transaction has had a transformative impact on Nigeria's economy by driving the expansion of digital payment and e-commerce. It is hoped that it will continue to play vital roles in driving economic growth and development in Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

The estimated results for the PPMCC or 'r' coefficients and the Coefficient of Determination (r^2) standing at 0.7574 and 57.37% respectively mean that the model passed the overall test of significance. From the foregoing report, we rejected the null hypothesis of no relationship and accepted the alternate hypothesis affirming that a strong and positive relationship subsists between Digital Wallet systems in operations and GDP Increase. More clearly, we imply that the adoption of Digital Wallet system operations in Nigeria has strongly facilitated Economic growth in the Nigerian economy. From the results showing high degree of relationship as displayed by the two computed parameters, we conclude that Digital Wallets adoption made relevant and great contributions to boosting commercial activities and transactions and thus facilitated GDP Increase in Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

From the findings, the study recommends effective enlightenment and education for the adoption of Digital Wallet system particularly among rural dwellers to boost the concept of financial inclusion being initiated by government and aimed at increasing economic activities. Since Digital wallet or mobile payment system has the capability to drive economic growth in Nigeria it is also recommended that the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in partner with banks should initiate and formulate allied policies that would enhance rapid acceptance of Digital wallet system in the economy. Finally, we recommend that there should be strong and efficient security and privacy measures to check the level of fraud, and personal information (data). This becomes very necessary because security is a major reason why so many individuals find it difficult to embrace Digital wallet system operations. These individuals should be encouraged and may need education on encryption and tokenization to mitigate their security threats.

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